

A Study on Solid State Thermal Decomposition Characteristics of Some Metallo-organic Compounds. Part-I : Dehydration and Decarboxylation of Hydrated Calcium Salts of Pyridine Monocarboxylic Acids

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Solid state dehydration of hydrated calcium salts of picolinic acid, nicotinic acid and isonicotinic acid and subsequent decarboxylation of the corresponding anhydrous salts have been studied by simultaneous TG, DTA and DTG techniques. From the analysis of the TG, DTA and DTG traces for the dehydration of the hydrated salts, the thermal stability order of the hydrates has been found to be $\text{Ca}(\text{pic})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{Ca}(\text{isoNic})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{Ca}(\text{Nic})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. But the trend observed in the decarboxylation process is $\text{Ca}(\text{Nic})_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{isoNic})_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{pic})_2$. Thermal parameters like activation energy, enthalpy change and order of reaction for each process have been computed by standard methods. An attempt has been made to correlate the trend in the thermal stability of the anhydrous salts towards decarboxylation with their molecular structure.

THE calcium salts were prepared by the reaction of a slight excess of CaCO_3 (G.R., E. Merck) with the appropriate acids in hot aqueous solutions followed by filtration and subsequent crystallisation.

Simultaneous DTA, TG and DTG determinations of the salts were carried out with a Paulik-Paulik-Erdey type MOM Derivatograph with dry air as the atmospheric gas. The particle size of the samples was in the 100-150 mesh range. The heating rate was about 4.25° per minute and sample size of 180-210 mg was used to make the volume nearly the same in each case. The reference material was aluminium oxide previously heated to 1600° . The sample holder and the reference holder were made of platinum. TG curves were utilised for calculating the activation energies of the processes involved, whereas DTA curves were used to evaluate the enthalpy changes accompanying the reactions. The initial, peak and final temperatures for the dehydration and the decarboxylation processes were noted from the corresponding DTG curves. The hydrated calcium salts and their dehydrated varieties were characterised by recording their IR spectra in halocarbon mull on a Beckman IR 70A model spectrophotometer. All the hydrated and the anhydrous compounds were analysed for calcium by titration with a standard EDTA solution. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined by microanalytical techniques.

Results and Discussions

Dehydration process : On gradual heating from room temperature, the hydrated salts were completely dehydrated within the temperature range

39° - 240° . From the TG, DTG and DTA traces of the dehydration stage it was found that all the dehydrations occurred in one step. All these processes might be represented by the general equation : $\text{Ca}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{Ca}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2 + x\text{H}_2\text{O}$; when $x=1$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2^-$ = picolinate ion; $x=3$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2^-$ = nicotinate ion; $x=4$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2^-$ = isonicotinate ion.

Initial, peak and final temperatures of the dehydration of each species, as obtained from the relevant DTG curves along with the corresponding weight loss are given in Table 1. Enthalpy changes accompanying dehydration of each species were determined by standard methods from the peak area of the corresponding DTA curves using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the standard¹. Activation energies for each dehydration process were computed from an analysis of the corresponding TG curves using the method of Horowitz and

Metzger² and the $\ln \ln \frac{W_0 - W_i}{W - W_i}$ vs θ plots are pre-

sented in Fig. 2. The order of reaction was determined by standard methods^{3,4} and was found to be unity. The results obtained are presented in Table 1 and the corresponding curves presented in Fig. 1. IR spectra of the hydrated and the anhydrous varieties were recorded and compared to ascertain the completion of the dehydration process.

Decarboxylation processes : All the anhydrous salts exhibit considerable thermal stability and undergo decarboxylation within the temperature range 340° - 600° . Initial, peak and final temperatures for the decarboxylation processes of the anhydrous

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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

the $\ln \ln \frac{W_0 - W_t}{W - W_t}$ vs θ plots, given in Fig. 3.

Enthalpy changes accompanying each decarboxylation process were measured from the DTA curves and are presented in Table 2. The order for the decarboxylation reactions was found to be unity in all the three cases. The corresponding curves are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 3

salts along with the corresponding weight losses are given in Table 2. The final product left in the crucible was found to be CaCO_3 . This has been confirmed by comparing the X-ray diffraction pattern of the end product with that of a pure CaCO_3 sample. Applying the same methods used in the dehydration processes, activation energies of the decarboxylation processes were evaluated from

TABLE 1

Reaction	Initiation temp. °C	Peak temp. °C	Completion temp. °C	Loss in wt. %		E _{Act} Kcal/mole	ΔH Kcal/mole	Order of reaction
				Calcd.	Found			
1. Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ ·3H ₂ O → Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ + 3H ₂ O Calcium nicotinate trihydrate	99	90	120	15.97	16	15.55	46.37	1
2. Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ ·4H ₂ O → Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ + 4H ₂ O Calcium isonicotinate tetrahydrate	82	130	215	20.22	20	22.96	62.07	1
3. Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ ·H ₂ O → Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ + H ₂ O Calcium picolinate monohydrate	160	193	240	5.96	5.88	52.13	26.24	1

TABLE 2

Reaction	Initiation temp. °C	Peak temp. °C	Completion temp. °C	Loss in wt. %		E _{Act} Kcal/mole	ΔH Kcal/mole	Order of reaction
				Calcd.	Found			
4. Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ → CaCO ₃ + products Calcium nicotinate	432	560	622	64.78	60.84	76.14	166.3	1
5. Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ → CaCO ₃ + products Calcium isonicotinate	385	486	620	64.78	64.83	50.85	44.46	1
6. Ca(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂ → CaCO ₃ + products Calcium picolinate	380	442	540	64.78	65.98	14.86	20.37	1

Solid state thermal decomposition of the salts of aromatic or heterocyclic acids has received little attention from the kinetic point of view. Most of the workers, who studied the thermal decomposition of the salts of organic acids (mostly aliphatic acids) in the solid state, used the maximum point method⁴⁻⁶ and the Freeman-Carroll method⁷ for the determination of the kinetic parameters. In the present work we have utilised Horowitz and Metzger's method, an analytical technique which utilises a single TG plot to determine the pertinent Arrhenius parameters and reaction order. The values obtained by the application of this method have been verified by the Coats and Redfern⁸ method wherever possible. We have utilised the DTA curves for the evaluation of enthalpy changes for the dehydration as well as decarboxylation processes.

The single step dehydration of calcium nicotinate trihydrate and the calcium isonicotinate tetrahydrate indicated that all the water molecules in the nicotinate trihydrate are similarly bound and such is also the case with the water molecules in the calcium isonicotinate tetrahydrate. A single endotherm in each of the DTA curves definitely points to the accuracy of the above conclusion. In the single step dehydration of all the three hydrates represented by the general equation in Table 1, the activation energies and enthalpy changes of dehydration are in the order picolinate > isonicotinate > nicotinate. This difference in thermal stabilities of the hydrates may be attributed to the differences in the mode of binding of the water molecules in the crystals of the three different pyridine monocarboxylates. It may thus be concluded that the water molecules in calcium picolinate are more firmly bound than those in isonicotinate and nicotinate and the water molecules in the calcium isonicotinate are held more strongly in comparison to those present in the calcium nicotinate.

In the decarboxylation of the anhydrous salts represented by equations given in Table 2, the activation energy follows the order nicotinate > isonicotinate > picolinate. The enthalpy change in the decarboxylation process also follows the same order.

It may be concluded from the data in Table 2 that the thermal stabilities of the carboxylates follow the order nicotinate > isonicotinate > picolinate. This trend is quite logical as the negatively charged carboxylate ion has a +I effect⁹ and hence releases electrons with a consequent increase of electron density on the ring carbon atom which, if present in a benzene ring, would have stabilized the ring carbon-carboxyl carbon bond. But in the present case, as the ring is a heterocyclic ring, the nitrogen atom being much more electronegative than carbon, would change the situation significantly and we find that unlike benzene, electron density distribution in the pyridine ring⁹ is as follows:

Due to the *ortho-para* orienting influence of the carboxylate ion the positions *ortho* and *para* to the ring carbon containing the carboxylate ion will have greater electron density and in the case of calcium picolinate, where the electronegative nitrogen atom is present in the position *ortho* to the ring carbon containing the carboxylate ion, it conveniently draws away this excess electron cloud towards itself and consequently reduces the electron cloud accumulated on the adjacent ring carbon atom considerably. It thus weakens the ring carbon-carboxylate carbon bond to a significant extent making it comparatively thermolabile.

In the case of the 4-picolinate anion, the enhanced electron density in the position *para* with respect to the carboxylate ion is accommodated on the nitrogen atom as a result of which the 4-carbon atom is relieved of some of its electron cloud acquired from the carboxylate anion and results in the weakening of the ring carbon-carboxyl carbon bond and consequently induces thermolability. But overall destabilisation effect is greater in 2-picolinate than in 4-picolinate due to the closeness of the ring nitrogen to the carboxylate substituent in the former and makes the 4-picolinate thermally more stable than the 2-picolinate compound. In the case of the 3-picolinate, the *ortho-para* orienting carboxylate ion would again result in electron enrichment in the *ortho* and *para* positions leaving the *meta* position unaffected. Thus, the increased electron density on the ring carbon atom containing the carboxylate ion is not decreased in this case. This leads to the stabilisation of the ring carbon-carboxyl bond when compared to the 2- and 4-picolinates and makes the 3-picolinate thermally stabler than the other two. Thus, the thermal stability order nicotinate > isonicotinate > picolinate, observed in this study, is quite in accordance with the theoretical principles.

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